

TIPPING THE SCALES: AN EXAMINATION OF TEXTBOOK TASKS IN THE CONTEXT OF CURRICULUM REFORM

Brendan O'Sullivan

School of Mathematical Sciences, Dublin City University

This paper is concerned with the analysis of mathematical textbook tasks at second-level in Ireland, in the context of the introduction of the revised curriculum initiative entitled 'Project Maths'. A total of 7635 tasks on the topics of Pattern, Sequences and Series and Differential Calculus contained in three textbook series for senior cycle, in editions available before and those available after the curriculum change, were analysed. The analysis presented here was informed by the use of a framework: Usiskin's multidimensional model of mathematical understanding (Usiskin, 2012). The research question considered is: what kind of understanding (using Usiskin's dimensions) is being promoted in the tasks analysed? The use of high quality tasks that promote understanding helps to maintain a high level of mathematical literacy. My findings suggest that the post-'Project Maths' textbook tasks offer greater opportunities in the area of mathematical understanding when compared to those in the older textbooks, but that there is still scope for further development. Based on my analysis, it would appear that all three textbook series have neglected important aspects like reasoning-and-proving and real life applications. Furthermore, the findings indicate that there is a need for more balance in tasks to ensure greater proficiency in mathematical literacy.

INTRODUCTION

This paper reports on part of a study concerned with the analysis of mathematical textbook tasks at second level in Ireland, in the context of the introduction of the revised curriculum entitled 'Project Maths'. The aim of the study was to gain greater insight into the nature of tasks that students and teachers work with in Irish classrooms by using five different frameworks. This paper will focus on reporting the results found using one of these frameworks: Usiskin's multidimensional model of mathematical understanding (Usiskin, 2012).

Textbooks have always been regarded as having an important role within the mathematics curriculum (Fan, Zhu & Miao, 2013). They can be seen as a link between the intended and the implemented curriculum, serving as the potentially implemented curriculum (Valverde, Bianchi, Wolfe, Schmidt & Houang, 2002). Research in relation to the implemented curriculum has shown that in several countries, mathematics textbooks can influence classroom instruction. Teachers often follow a sequence of topics as suggested by textbooks and much of the work completed in class is drawn from textbooks (Lepik 2015, Eisenmann & Even 2011, Haggarty & Pepin 2002). The situation is no different in Ireland, where it is reported that a lot of the time in the classroom appears to be related to the textbook and very often it is the only resource which students have access to during the lesson aside from the teacher, while most of the problems assigned for classwork and homework come from the textbook (Project Maths, 2017). As questions from textbooks would normally be assigned as classwork or given to students for homework (Hourigan & O'Donoghue, 2007, p. 471), these

tasks provide an insight into the teaching and learning taking place in Irish classrooms. In this paper, the following research question is considered. What kind of understanding (using Usiskin's dimensions) is being promoted in the textbook tasks analysed? The framework is used to classify tasks on the topic of Pattern, Sequences and Series and Differential Calculus from three popular Irish textbook series.

CONTEXT: THE IMPACT OF 'PROJECT MATHS'

A number of reports have been published in relation to 'Project Maths' and its impact. The National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA) (NCCA, 2012) in its response to the debate on 'Project Maths' notes that textbooks have traditionally supported practising routine questions with solutions based on illustrative examples. The report calls for more emphasis to be given to students engaging in problem-solving approaches and justifying or explaining their solutions (NCCA, 2012, p. 18).

The NCCA also commissioned a report (Jeffes, Jones, Wilson, Lamont, Straw, Wheeler and Dawson, 2013) exploring the impact of 'Project Maths' on student learning and achievement in the initial pilot schools that introduced the syllabus in 2008 and the remaining schools in the country that introduced it in 2010. The new syllabuses were introduced on a phased basis. There are five strands at senior cycle in total: 1) Statistics and Probability, 2) Geometry and Trigonometry, 3) Number, 4) Algebra and 5) Functions. Strands 1 and 2 were introduced in 24 Pilot Schools in 2008 and in all other schools in 2010. Strands 3 and 4 followed in 2009 for the pilot schools and in 2011 for the remaining cohort, while the final strand was introduced in 2010 and 2012 respectively.

One of the main findings of this report (Jeffes et al., 2013, p. 3) is that more traditional approaches like using textbooks and copying from the whiteboard continue to be widespread. The report suggests that students need to be regularly given high quality tasks that require them to engage with the processes promoted by 'Project Maths', including: problem-solving; drawing out connections between mathematics topics; communicating more effectively in written form; and justifying and providing evidence for their answers.

A Chief Examiner's Report (State Examinations Commission, 2016) in Leaving Certificate mathematics was published in 2016, the first of its kind published after the introduction of the 'Project Maths' syllabus. It reviewed candidates' performance in the 2015 examinations and set itself the goal of identifying strengths and challenges in order to provide guidance for teachers and students in the future (SEC, 2016). It noted that the syllabus expectations are more ambitious than previously and are not always easy to achieve; the authors commented that there has been a deliberate attempt to emphasise higher order thinking skills but acknowledged that this presents difficulties for both students and teachers alike (SEC, 2016, p. 8). The report recommended that students should become more familiar with describing, explaining, justifying and providing examples. It noted that these skills assist with improving understanding (SEC, 2016, p. 9). Teachers were also reminded to encourage students to practise solving problems involving real-life applications of mathematics. As part of this process, students should be asked to model these situations by constructing algebraic

expressions or equations and/or representing them differently by drawing diagrams (SEC, 2016, p. 30). Similarly the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) produced a report to offer advice to teachers in relation to the findings from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2012 and strategies for teaching and learning. The report recommends that teachers should encourage students to think more deeply about what has been learned and encourage the establishment of connections with real-world problems (OECD, 2016, p. 38).

Textbook Studies

O’Keeffe and O’Donoghue (2012) conducted a study of the textbooks published in response to ‘Project Maths’ that were available at the time (ten in all). The study found that all textbooks analysed fell short of the standard needed to support the ‘Project Maths’ (intended) curriculum effectively, as outlined in the ‘Project Maths’ syllabus documents for junior cycle and senior cycle, but that some of the new textbooks were better aligned to ‘Project Maths’ expectations than others.

Davis (2013) examined the prevalence of reasoning-and-proving in the topic of complex numbers in six Irish textbooks and one teaching and learning plan produced for teachers during the introduction of the ‘Project Maths’ curricular initiative. His study uses a framework consisting of five main components: namely pattern identification, conjecture development, argument construction, technological tools, and reasoning-and-proving objects. Only 1.4% of tasks in Ordinary Level textbooks and 1.3% of tasks in Higher Level textbooks involved pattern identification or conjecture development. There were no opportunities to test conjectures, construct counterexamples or develop proof subcomponents in any of the materials examined. The results from Davis’ study suggest that the six textbook units do not align with the syllabus introduced as part of ‘Project Maths’ (Davis, 2013, p. 54).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Usiskin (2012) deals with the understanding of a concept in mathematics from the standpoint of the learner and how the learner interacts with it. Usiskin’s multi-dimensional framework is not limited to a consideration of instrumental and relational understanding as categorised by Skemp (1976). A number of other dimensions are introduced to achieve this. Five dimensions of this understanding are outlined in his framework: the Skill-Algorithm dimension, the Property-Proof dimension, the Use-Application (modelling) dimension, the Representation-Metaphor dimension and the History-Culture dimension. The term ‘dimension’ is used because each element can be accessed independently of the others. These dimensions are not presented in a hierarchy; it is possible for each to co-exist and one aspect is not meant to precede another. As a framework, it can provide a comprehensive examination of learning.

The first dimension Skill-Algorithm looks at the algorithms that are necessary for the learning of a concept and the choice of a particular algorithm because it is more efficient than other algorithms known. Property-Proof understanding identifies the mathematical properties that underlie a concept. This aspect of learning goes deeper, looking beyond arbitrary rules and considering the mathematical theory behind them. Use-Application understanding focuses on

the applications of a concept or how it can be used in some way. The Representation-Metaphor dimension encourages the representation of a concept in some way. Finally History-Culture understanding concerns itself with the how and why of the development of a mathematical concept over time. The History-Culture dimension is an aspect that is identified by Usiskin as necessary for the ‘real true’ understanding. The premise is that those who study the history of mathematics or cross-cultural mathematics obtain an understanding of mathematical concepts that is different from the other dimensions.

Example of classification of a task using the framework

An artificial ski slope is described by the function

$$h = 165 - 120s + 60s^2 - 10s^3$$

where s is the horizontal distance and h is the height of the slope. Show that the ski slope never rises.

Three of Usiskin’s dimensions are evident here.

- Skill-Algorithm: the student can use a model to find the derivative and to prove that the function is always decreasing.
- Property-Proof: Proving that the ski slope never rises. (Function always decreasing).
- Use-Application: The ski slope is a real life situation.

METHODOLOGY

For this work, a task is considered to be an activity where a student interacts with a mathematical topic by attempting to solve a question either as homework or within the classroom. This is in keeping with Mason and Johnston-Wilder’s definition (2006, p.4) that a task is what learners are asked to do in the mathematics classroom.

It was decided to focus on the senior cycle material in particular because of the high-stakes (Leaving Certificate) examination that accompanies it. Textbook tasks on the topics of Pattern, Sequences and Series, and Differential Calculus are considered here. These topics were chosen because they are present on both Higher and Ordinary Level Leaving Certificate Mathematics syllabuses and both were also present on the previous syllabus. Also the topic of Pattern, Sequences and Series was introduced in the first phase of the syllabus implementation while Differential Calculus was in the final stage. I analysed tasks from three textbook series available on the Irish market: referred to as Textbook A, Textbook B and Textbook C. These three textbook series were selected because they were the first to be published in response to the new curriculum, while they have also traditionally been the most popular in Irish classrooms.

From the six pre-‘Project Maths’ and six post-‘Project Maths’ textbooks, each chapter relating to Patterns, Sequences and Series and Differential Calculus was analysed. A total of 7635 tasks (3584 pre-‘Project Maths’ and 4051 post-‘Project Maths’) were classified from the chapters chosen. It was necessary to discard 16 tasks from the analysis when ambiguity was

encountered (for example, where a misprint made it difficult to interpret what a task required). Questions sometimes consisted of several parts and it was necessary to break these up and treat them as multiple tasks. Several checks were made over time to ensure that what was treated as a task in one textbook was consistent with the other five textbooks regardless of how exercises were structured or presented.

After I had coded the textbook tasks, at least one of my two PhD supervisors also looked at each task separately and we compared our classifications after each framework analysis was complete. We then discussed any of the classifications that we had differences on and gave our perspective on why we analysed them as we did, coming to agreement on how the coding should be applied. Having clarified and resolved our coding, we made any necessary revisions and reviewed the existing classifications of previous tasks in light of these revisions, in order to ensure consistency throughout the analysis. This led to a final set of classifications. It should be noted that a single task can have multiple dimensions present and the percentages in the tables in the following section will not total to 100%.

RESULTS

Table 1 contains the results of the classification of the exercises on the topic of Pattern, Sequences and Series and Differential Calculus in the three textbook series under consideration. It shows the number and percentage of tasks falling into each classification for both the pre- and post- ‘Project Maths’ eras. In Table 2, each of the three textbook series at Higher and Ordinary level published for the post-‘Project Maths’ era are classified in terms of the five dimensions of understanding.

Table 1: Classification of tasks using Usiskin’s Multidimensional Model in pre- and post- ‘Project Maths’ textbooks

	Pre-‘Project Maths’ Textbook Series average	Post-‘Project Maths’ Textbook Series average
Skill-Algorithm	3556 (99.22%)	3909 (96.49%)
Property-Proof	181 (5.05%)	382 (9.43%)
Use-Application	237 (6.61%)	655 (16.17%)
Representation-Metaphor	107 (2.99%)	706 (17.43%)
History-Culture	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

All three series have a high incidence of the Skill-Algorithm dimension at both Higher and Ordinary level in Usiskin’s dimensions of mathematical understanding. Of the remaining dimensions, the textbook A series has the greatest incidence of the Property-Proof and Representation-Metaphor dimensions at Higher and Ordinary level. The textbook C series has the greatest number of tasks corresponding to the Use-Application category at both Higher and Ordinary level.

Table 2: Classification of tasks using Usiskin’s Multidimensional Model for post- ‘Project Maths’ textbooks

	Skill- Algorithm	Property- Proof	Use- Application	Representation- Metaphor	History- Culture
Textbook A Higher Level	846 95%	117 13.1%	133 14.9%	187 21%	0 0%
Textbook A Ordinary Level	630 97.4%	67 10.4%	103 15.9%	180 27.8%	0 0%
Textbook B Higher Level	605 95.9%	55 8.7%	66 10.5%	81 12.8%	0 0%
Textbook B Ordinary Level	457 97%	35 7.4%	91 19.3%	84 17.8%	0 0%
Textbook C Higher Level	822 98.9%	58 7%	136 16.4%	53 6.4%	0 0%
Textbook C Ordinary Level	549 94.7%	50 8.6%	126 21.7%	121 20.9%	0 0%

With Usiskin’s multidimensional model, an increase was recorded in the three dimensions of Representation-Metaphor, Property-Proof and Use-Application yet a much greater incidence would be desirable. Despite modest improvements, it would appear that students would benefit from greater exposure to more varied tasks. The Chief Examiner’s Report has recommended that students should become more familiar with the processes of description, explanation, justification and the provision of examples. It noted that ‘these are skills that are worth practising, as they will improve understanding’ (SEC, 2016, p. 30). The NCCA in its report responding to the debate on the ‘Project Maths’ curriculum and its introduction called for more emphasis to be given to students engaging in problem-solving approaches and justifying or explaining their solutions (NCCA, 2012, p. 18). Similarly the report on the impact of ‘Project Maths’ in pilot schools (Jeffes et al., 2013) observed that students are building up expertise with the use of procedures. The report also noted that students are problem-solving and making mathematical representations but to a lesser extent than using procedures. An absence of engagement with reasoning and proof, communicating mathematically, or making connections between mathematics topics was also observed. It would appear that the textbooks do not support this goal adequately and teachers will need to augment existing tasks to achieve it. The Chief Examiner’s Report has acknowledged that the syllabus expectations are more ambitious than previously and that they are not necessarily easy to achieve; ‘there has been a deliberate attempt to increase the emphasis on higher-order

thinking skills. These are skills that students find difficult to master and teachers may find difficult to instil' (SEC, 2016, p. 9).

A key concern arising from my analysis is the lack of balance in the textbook tasks analysed. Swan and Burkhardt (2012) have suggested principles for task design suitable for use as assessment. These principles could also be used when designing tasks suitable for use in the classroom and/or for homework. They suggest that a balanced series of tasks should meet all the different goals and objectives that the curriculum aspires to. This is something that the textbook tasks do not currently achieve in relation to the 'Project Maths' curriculum according to my analysis. It is also recommended that tasks should be viewed by students as something interesting or having a potential use outside of the classroom. The lack of Usiskin's History-Culture dimension and the relatively low incidence of the Use-Application dimension in my analysis would suggest that the Irish textbook tasks do not currently achieve this.

The area of reasoning-and-proving is worthy of attention, I found that there was a low incidence of tasks classified in the property-proof dimension of Usiskin's framework and in general, very few of the tasks classified required the explanation of findings or the justification of conclusions. These results are also supported by Davis' (2013) analysis. It appears that more tasks are required in order to encourage students to engage in creative reasoning, explain findings, justify conclusions and communicate their mathematical thoughts. Jeffes et al. (2013) also highlight this when they call for tasks that involve students in 'communicating more effectively in written form; and justifying and providing evidence for their answers'. In fact, they called for high quality tasks 'to engage with the processes promoted by the revised syllabuses, including: problem-solving; drawing out connections between mathematics topics' (p.32). Teachers will have to take care in the classroom, if not doing so already, to encourage students to verify their solutions, solve tasks using several methods and to explain their mathematical thinking when completing tasks.

REFERENCES

- Davis, J. D. (2013). Examining reasoning-and-proving in the treatment of complex numbers in Irish secondary mathematics textbooks. *Bulletin of the Irish Mathematical Society*, 71, 41-57.
- Eisenmann, T., & Even, R. (2011). Enacted types of algebraic activity in different classes taught by the same teacher. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 9(4), 867-891.
- Fan, L., Zhu, Y., & Miao, Z. (2013). Textbook research in mathematics education: Development status and directions. *ZDM: International Journal on Mathematics Education*, 45(5), 633-646.
- Haggarty, L., & Pepin, B. (2002). An investigation of mathematics textbooks and their use in English, French and German classrooms: Who gets an opportunity to learn what? *British Educational Research Journal*, 28(4), 567-590.

- Hourigan, M., & O'Donoghue, J. (2007). Mathematical under-preparedness: the influence of the pre-tertiary mathematics experience on students' ability to make a successful transition to tertiary level mathematics courses in Ireland. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 38(4), 461-476.
- Jeffes, J., Jones, E., Wilson, M., Lamont, E., Straw, S., Wheater, R. & Dawson, A. (2013). Research into the impact of Project Maths on student achievement, learning and motivation: Final report. Slough: NFER.
- Lepik, M. (2015). Analyzing the use of textbook in mathematics education: The case of Estonia. *Acta Paedagogica Vilnensia*, 35, 90-102.
- Mason, J. & Johnston-Wilder, S. (2006). *Designing and Using Mathematical Tasks*. St. Albans: Tarquin Publications.
- Moffett, P. (2009). Reform via textbooks: Lessons from a cross-national collaboration. In D. Corcoran, T. Dooley, S. Close, R. Ward (Eds.), *Proceedings of Third National Conference on Research in Mathematics Education*, (pp. 262-272). Dublin: MEI.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2012). Project Maths responding to current debate. Retrieved from http://www.ncca.ie/en/Publications/Other_Publications/Project-Maths-Responding-to-Current-Debate.pdf
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2016). Ten questions for mathematics teachers ... and how PISA can help answer them. PISA, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- O'Keeffe, L., & O'Donoghue, J. (2012). *A Review of School Textbooks for Project Maths*. National Centre for Excellence in Mathematics and Science Teaching and Learning (NCE-MSTL), Limerick.
- Project Maths. (2017). Retrieved from <https://www.projectmaths.ie/for-teachers/explanation-of-resources/textbooks/>
- Skemp R. R. (1976). Relational understanding and instructional understanding. *Mathematics Teacher*, 77(1):20-26.
- State Examinations Commission. (2016). Leaving Certificate Examination 2015 Mathematics: Chief Examiner's report. Retrieved from <https://www.examinations.ie/misc-doc/EN-EN-53913274.pdf>
- Swan, M., & Burkhardt, H. (2012). Designing assessment of performance in mathematics. *Educational Designer*, 2(5).
- Usiskin, Z. (2012). What does it mean to understand some Mathematics? Retrieved from <http://www.amesa.org.za/AMESA2013/Files/P01.pdf>
- Valverde, G. A., Bianchi, L. J., Wolfe, R. G., Schmidt, W. H. & Houang, R. T. (2002). *According to the book: Using TIMSS to investigate the transition of policy into practice through the world of textbooks*. Springer Science & Business Media